

MACROPRUDENTIAL POLICY GUIDELINES AND BANKING SYSTEM SOUNDNESS: A HOMOGENOUS CROSS-COUNTRY ANALYSIS OF MACRO-FINANCIAL NEXUS

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<p>Keyword: Macroprudential Policy, Financial Stability, Credit Boom, GMM, Business Cycle</p> <p>JEL Codes: E51, C23, E32</p>	<p>Abstract: The relationship between macroprudential policy guidelines and financial stability is indirectly associated with the economy. The association is derived under the assumption that in the absence of elevated systemic vulnerability bank financial intermediation provides uninterrupted supply of liquidity and sustainable workings of payment infrastructure. The current study conducts investigations on globally recognized macro prudential policy instruments vis-à-vis financial soundness of the banking system. Country-level data are collected on a large panel of 102 Middle and Low Incomes countries. All data are available in World Bank, International Monetary Fund, domestic central banks and regional development banks collected in the last 9 years. In addition, Hodrick-Prescott filter is used to construct business cycle observations. Appropriate estimation procedures cover unbalanced panel data analytical technique consisting Ordinary Least Square, Within Group, Generalized Methods of Moments and Two Stage Least square required for instrumental variable. According to baseline regression, current accounts deficits, interest rate and credits boom show disruptive effects on banking system soundness by impairing quality of first-tier common equity. Our result further showed that regulatory governance interaction with macro prudential policy instruments, confirms that regulatory governance is less effective in containing business cycle tendency to damage banking system soundness. Conversely, robust regulation is significantly effective in mitigating credits boom adverse consequences on soundness and stability in some countries banking system.</p>
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Introduction
 Financial system businesses make them vulnerable to different risk classes. Sudden occurrence of systemic risk events could be devastating to the financial sector. Underlying fundamental causes of systemic crisis that

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undermine banking soundness across financial system varies. What is well known is that anti-bank stability forces abound. From the point of market, Hennig, Iossifov and Varghese (2023) established rapid asset price growth and low asset price volatility as signals for future financial crises. Although individual bank errors and market turmoil notably slide the industry into systemic bankruptcy in advanced economies (O'Sullivan & Kennedy, 2010; Fujii & Kawai, 2012; Hirakata et al, 2016), accidental mismanagement of macroeconomics plays similar role in emerging markets and developing economies (Mishkin, 1996). In a clear instance, Wyplosz (1998) underscores Mexican debt defaults in 1982; whereas Graf (1999) reveals that currency crisis from devaluation and subsequent sharp contraction of the economy worsened Mexican banking crisis in 1994. Sizeable build-up of credits has been known and forms part of the rationale (Dell'Araccia & Marques, 2006). On the other hand, the banking system can be under intense threat where a single bank contributes adverse risks to member financial institutions. Often a single country risk manifestation disrupts financial stability of several countries interconnected in the financial system network. This has been manifestly present in more developed financial systems especially among those in monetary union (Downes, Marston & Ötoker, 1999; Bjarnadottir, 2012). Such random occurrence intermittently erupts from Global Systemic Important Banks (G-SIB) spilling over

to other smaller locally active banks without history of cross-border business profile. This is fundamentally why micro prudential policy is regrettably obsolete.

A global policy concern is maintenance and sustenance of stability of the financial system (Chang, 2016; Central Bank of Egypt, 2023; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2022; Central Bank of Ireland (2024a, 2024b)). Across different jurisdictions it is a longstanding responsibility of central banks. Crystallization of systemic risks consequences exposed dangers in depending on micro prudential policy when in reality risks could be contagiously systemic. Macro prudential policy is often discussed separately from outdated micro prudential policy. The former is seen as taking a system-wide and often time-varying approach to risk while micro prudential policy is said to take an institution-specific approach, focusing on ensuring that individual financial institutions are resilient to shocks by applying appropriate risk management frameworks (Hilbers et al. 2000; Orsmond & Price, 2016; Guindos, 2018). However, these two policies generally complement and reinforce each other since sound individual financial institutions support a stable financial system while a stable financial system supports the soundness of individual institutions.

Macro prudential guidelines strengthen the banking system in a superior way by addressing risks from group of interdependent financial corporations while it is also alert to dynamics

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from macroeconomic dynamics, hence, averting systemic bank collapse capable of spilling disturbances into the real sector or whereas it also blocks reverse contagion flowing from distressed real and foreign sectors that increase financial system vulnerability. The rising prominence of macro prudential policy in the global economic policy is rooted in the hurtful experience of powerful financial systems during the last global financial crisis and eventual economic meltdown (Catte et al. 2011; Benigno et al. 2013; Jeanne, 2014; Forbes, 2021; Epure et al. 2024). For countries classified as developing and emerging markets whose financial system is dominated by depository corporations, manipulating macro prudential variables provide protective shield against systemic risks materialization that disrupt liquidity supplies. Monitoring prudential situations of the banking system in advanced and developing countries have since intensified. Thus far, in Hilbers et al. (2000); Claessens (2015); Banco de Cabo Verde (2017); Central Bank of Gambia (2018); Kozlovceva et al. (2020) insights are handful national experiences in combination with emerging institutional working papers documenting conceptual, theoretical and empirical literature provide extensive information about macro prudential indicators (MPIs) as well as contemporaneous factors that mirror and possess capacity to preserve banking system soundness. Banque Centrale des Etats de l'Afrique de l'Ouest (BCEAO) (2023); Bank of

Tanzania (2023, 2017); National Bank of Kazakhstan (2023); Boissay et al. (2023) provide highly informative thinking on promoting governance of financial system stability through macro prudential policy. Unfortunately, since the last Global Financial Crisis (GFC), research tradition seems to have consistently favored housing sector when undertaking macro prudential study tasks. Why is this a norm in earlier research investigations? Perhaps classic explanation could be due to the notorious mortgage market crisis evolution when crash in property price distributed systemic risk across distant financial systems. Evidently, the aftermath was the last global economic meltdown. Wong et al. (2011); Bank for International Settlements (2023); Robinson (2023); Peterson (2023) are accompanying macro prudential policy studies dedicated to housing market crisis. The literature on financial system soundness is rich. However, while it is established that macro prudential policy plays a leading role, it goes way back that vast majority of research publications produce investigations that have revolutionized our understanding of cost of systemic risk. Constâncio et al. (2019) disclose permanent loss of outputs as opportunity cost. Research concerns have not been fully addressed. Less is known on how shocks in the macro-financial environment affect banking soundness- or, more accurately perhaps, what classes of such exogenous variables integrated with micro prudential conditions are more

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prominent. Top macroeconomic variable as business cycle in the economy and balance of payments' current account deficits crucially raise important question about financial system resilience. Avom et al. (2023) macro-financial shock consequences on banking system resilience in CEMAC provide fine highlights, yet it is rigid in scope with Cameroon's extreme influence in sub-regional economy more evident in finding. Empirical literatures to the best of our knowledge have not provided substantial response. However, historic record of massive bank crisis in several advanced and developing countries dominate regulatory policy papers, empirical and theoretical literature (Wong, Wong & Fong, 2009; European Central Bank, 2023). Developing timely cross-country evidence is presently an important exercise in macro prudential analysis in potentially vulnerable banking systems. We set this issue in a wider context. This is because of instances of widespread experience of banking crises in good number of countries. Extreme consequences have made issue of financial system soundness even more relevant and topical. We replicate research in emerging market and developing economies (EMDEs). For clarification Middle and Low-income countries constitute EMDEs. We relate how dominant macroeconomic developments dictate banking system soundness using capital adequacy as benchmark. Financial stability and soundness are assessed in various territories using capital adequacy position of banks hinged

on core capital (Central Bank of Algeria, 2019; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2022; Banco Central Chile, 2023; Central Bank of Egypt, 2023; National Bank of Kazakhstan, 2023). Core capital consisting of equity and disclosed reserves has a crucial bearing on profit margins and a bank's ability to compete.

Our ultimate goal is to conduct investigation in the progressing field of macro prudential policy capacity to mitigate financial fragility which indirectly impact economic prosperity of some developing countries and emerging markets. Thus, responses to the following questions shall be provided:

- I. By how much does marginal changes in credit boom influence banking system soundness?
- II. To what extent does current account deficits in balance of payments exert adverse effects on banking system soundness?
- III. To what extent does nonperforming loans portfolio produce adjustments in banking system soundness?
- IV. How much does business cycles affect soundness of the banking system?
- V. What is the empirical connection between levels of domestic interest rates, soundness of the banking system?

Going forward the current study is segmented into sections. Therefore, the next is section 2 as literature review. Section 3 provides details on data and econometric specification. It is followed by section 4 as discussion of selected

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results. Study ends in section 5 on concluding remarks.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Framework of Macro prudential Policy Guidelines

Macro prudential policy guidelines are toolkits to withstand potential multi-faceted systemic risks sources facing the financial system. A definitive understanding is that macro prudential policy involve monitoring a large set of indicators, covering seven important areas in which experience and history have shown are prone to financial vulnerability (Nijathaworn, 2010). However, a generally agreed upon set of core indicators underpinning macro prudential monitoring guidelines are yet to be recorded unlike existing research consensus on aggregated micro prudential¹ indicators in research. We know there is ongoing scientific work on measurement and conceptual issues that are progressing rapidly. Clearly conceptualizing macro prudential policy guidelines is not quite easy because of relevance of component indicators that are

varied across regulatory jurisdictions. The country-to-country variation implies that indicators are not used mechanically, rather every comprehensive set of variables requires taking into account the overall structure and economic situation of a country and its financial system. From the early moments of development of MPIs, it is comprehensively defined as indicators of the health and stability of financial systems (BIS, 2000).

¹ As contained in Basel II Accord, micro prudential indicators are bank-level regulatory measures which help to reinforce resilience of individual banking enterprise during period of stress. A standard measurement framework to proxy micro prudential factors is the six banking regulatory components covered under the notable-CAMELS to diagnose the health of any bank or financial institutions. The components have been computed under the various BASEL Accords (Basel I, II and III) which also provide a rating system in banking supervision (Dang, 2011). See for instance, Gavalas and Syriopolous (2014); Iheanyi and Sotonye (2017); Nguyen, Nguyen and Pham (2020).

Table 2.1: Conceptual Basis of Macro prudential Policy Instruments

Instruments	Conceptual Basis and Effectiveness and Measures
Credits boom	Increases household and bank resilience through lower probability of default. Minimizing a boom in credit to the private sector while preventing bust cycle protects banking resilience.
Interest rate	Sharp increase in interest rates slows down capacity of borrower to repay debts; increase bank assets portfolio erosion rate. They add to stressful conditions for most banks.
Current accounts deficits	Large external current accounts deficits drain the liquidity of the financial system and could signal vulnerability to a currency crisis with negative implications for the liquidity of the financial system. Foreign investors may consider current account deficit unsustainably large motivating a shift of their financial investments out of the country.
Nonperforming loans	Prudential review of a bank’s lending and credit risk assessment is a function that determines quality of bank credits. None performing loans are bad loans which arise when the borrower no longer pays in accordance with the terms of the loan often linked to adverse selection.
Business cycle	Business cycle—measured as the cycle component of real GDP, computed using the Hodrick-Prescott filter.

Source: Grace, Hallissey and Woods (2015); Lee, Asuncion and Kim (2016)

2.1.1 Conceptual Review of Banking System Soundness

In this part, we document various information about individual bank’s soundness and the soundness of the entire system. Financial system stability concept is vastly employed in the literature than banking system soundness especially when performing global financial system analysis (IMF, 2023). Clearly, in this empirical task financial system soundness is akin to banking system soundness for developing countries whose major financial enterprises is ruled by conventional banks. Financial stability in its ramification entails an existence of a well-functional financial system which guarantees optimal consumption of

household and enterprises over time by intermediating between savers and borrowers, carry out payments and redistribute risk in a satisfactory manner (Gjedrem, 2005). These functional activities promote an efficient allocation of real economic resources across different activity sectors over time. Resilience is a standard measure of how a financial system stabilizes in its intermediation operation irrespective of any domestic and external shock magnitude. Several categories of risks can impair banking system soundness. Specifically, the financial sector is vulnerable to concentration, market, assets price, liquidity and solvency risks (Bank of Namibia, 2018). Official documents and empirics present

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various comparable factors explaining the extent a banking system is robust and sound.

Notable indicator of banking system health is the capital adequacy of the banks. Banks are expected to maintain capital adequacy ratio (CAR) that is slightly above regulatory minimum to absorb emerging shocks in the system. This is to ensure that credit advances and normal operations are not disrupted due to deteriorations in credit portfolio and business cycle. Capital adequacy ratio is manipulated according to Basel III benchmark. In reality all

jurisdictions normatively align their banking system with international prudential rule and standard of reference. National bodies have the autonomy to design financial system class of soundness variables. Figure 2.1.1 (panel A & B for UAE and China) displays national choices of financial system soundness indicators. Evidently, solvency (capital adequacy ratio), asset quality, profitability and liquidity variables are vital indices to evaluate capacity of the financial system to overcome vulnerability.

Figure 2.1.1: Banking System Soundness Selected Indicators (%)

Source: Author’s plot using data published by CBUAE and BBVA Research / China Banking Monitor

Financial system stability is a universal set of banking system soundness for reason of complete coverage of the entire national and cross-border financial institutions’ complex operational interconnectivity. However, this is a huge task given complex operations of some financial firms across various international² borders. Soundness of certain single bank can be tracked using micro prudential regulatory test instruments. Banks dominate the financial system and perfectly conveys bulk of its

information in the literature. We describe standard regulatory factors pointing to the health status of licensed banks that support their roles in the economy. Policymakers regularly adopt financial system stability to construct comprehensive profile of the financial system. It reveals the potential sources of vulnerability whose evolution could be traced to financial institutions outside conventional banks. Different jurisdictions have applied varying policy tools including the application of stress tests³ to detect financial sector

² For instance, HSBC Group has 110 million customers worldwide; Citigroup is present in about 100 countries and territories. Eco Bank plc has several customers in the West African sub-region as a pan African banking institution. Home grown Nigeria bank crossing to distant markets include: Access bank plc with market presence in DR Congo, Mozambique, The Gambia and beyond (Access bank, 2020). GTCO also has expanded African franchise on the continent (GTCO, 2020).

³ Stress approaches include four steps: (i) construction of base and adverse macroeconomic scenarios; (ii) clustering of banks in homogenous groups using statistical methods; (iii) estimation of the sensitivities of the probabilities of default and return on assets to economic conditions; and (iv) projected deterioration of bank portfolios and profitability under the baseline and adverse scenarios. See for example, IMF (2022) technical note on WAEMU.

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vulnerabilities to adverse shocks (Reserve Bank of Australia, 2012). Stress tests examine spectrum of factors affecting the banks. In the bank supervision reports there are (1) stress tests on credit, interest rate, and concentration risk (2) stress tests on solvency and interest rate stress tests (3) Stress tests on contagion and liquidity risks. On capital adequacy, Nigeria has imposed new statutory capital requirements across different bank categories. Stress test in WAEMU banks had also pointed to the importance of moderate new recapitalization needs in large banks of member countries (IMF, 2022).

Attaining banking system soundness in developed and developing economies has been an intriguing discuss for several years so important in every regulatory jurisdiction. However, a broader interest covering the entire financial system has taken over in policy papers and remains increasingly more dominant as the system is prone to crisis. Nigeria is no exception. Individual bank failures for whatever reason can amplify shocks in the economy. A sound banking system should be far removed from unexpected crisis episode due to stringent governance which ensures no disruption in credit intermediation process and payments. Policy documents and literature categorically point to elements portraying soundness in the banking system (Bank of Namibia, 2023). To this end the elements expressing soundness are very diverse. On the context of quality, Basel Committee on Bank Supervision (BCBS) conceptualizes banking

system soundness to indicate strong and resilience⁴banking sector.

2.1.2 Monetary Sector Survey in Developing Countries

The monetary sector in developing countries is simply the banking system intermediating functions. A complete survey of the sector is a consolidation of balance sheet of the banks and central banks. Using ECOWAS and CEMAC regional financial sector information there is strong similarity across developing countries monetary sector. It is bank dominated since presence and transactions of non-depository financial institutions are of less importance for economic roles. Monetary aggregates and situations in some countries coordinated by common central bank appear to behave in a somewhat unified way (BCEAO, 2020). Reserve requirements applicable to banks in year 2017 was a flat rate of 5.0% irrespective of the interior conditions in the WAEMU economies. However, monetary aggregates in the union reveals huge differences in their various financial sectors (fig. 2.1.2). Niger whose monetary aggregate is narrow compared to small countries of Togo and Benin republic may be hindered on any plan to macroeconomic progress.

⁴ see for instance, Banking Committee on Banking Supervision (2009) consultative document issued for comment by April 16, 2010.

Table 2.1.2: Reserve Requirement Ratios Applicable to Banks

	Benin	Burkina Faso	Côte d'Ivoire	Guine a-Bissau	Mali	Niger	Senegal	Togo
June 16, 2009 – May 15,2010	9.0	9.0	5.0	3.0	7.0	7.0	7.0	3.0
May 16 - Dec. 15 2010	7.0	7.0	5.0	5.0	7.0	7.0	7.0	5.0
Dec. 16, 2010 – March 15, 2012	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.0
March 16, 2012 – March 15, 2017	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
Since March 16, 2017	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0

Source: BCEAO (2017) annual report

Figure 2.1.2: Broad Money Supply in West African Developing Countries

Source: Author’s plot from assembled data available in BCEAO statistical bulletin

Broad money supply in Guinea-Bissau is small which implies investments in capital formation may not attract tangible amount of bank credits (BCEAO, 2017). It might suggest reason for their real sector small size. This is a huge constraint for industrialization. Côte d'Ivoire and Senegal monetary sectors are moderately more robust to sustain economic activities to grow the GDP. Tighter or loosed monetary policy could have more constraining or expanding effects in different magnitudes

across different countries. If the objective of imposing tighter monetary measure is to curb inflation it may disadvantage others even though it is suitable for volatile economies.

2.1.3 Specific Categories of Macro prudential Policy Variables

Several regulatory jurisdictions have come up with vast arrays of macro prudential policy conditions attracting banking system supervisory focus. Over time the numbers seem to be expanding due to perhaps, the sensitivity

of the financial system to severe and several social-economic situations that may eventually lead to gradual build-up of risk. Several policy documents shed impressive light on this issue (Borio & Shim, 2007). However, considering the current empirical research we concentrate on macro prudential dimensions relevant to our analysis.

2.1.3.1 Macro prudential Dimension: Lending Boom

Lending boom is often admitted in analytical models as a ratio of credit to gross domestic product. Lending forms a central part of the narrative of financial crises and financial cycles more generally (Drehmann et al. 2015). According to Saudi Central Bank (2024), a useful indicator to determine the buildup of vulnerabilities is a faster expansion in credit activities relative to economic activities. Credit-to-GDP is potentially a procyclical prudential tool that impacts financial system soundness. Excessive credit growth is harmful to the economic system when where productivity is slowing down. Lending boom tests household and business sector indebtedness vis-à-vis the level of productivity in the economy. This is where banks contribute to pro-cyclicality making the economy owe the financial institutions excess obligation that may not be redeemable in a timely manner. There is less concern if credit to private sector grows with private sector depth of productivity of which output is expected to be higher. It means indebted private sector economy has enough resources to offset loans. Obviously, what is clearly less known is the ideal comprehensive and comparative measure at the

interjurisdictional level what constitutes an excess credit level in the economy that current outputs cannot effectively liquidate. However, research suggests that a credit-to-GDP ratio above approximately 96.5% can significantly weaken the positive link between credit and economic growth. Yet, in the absence of straightforward theoretical foundations, all proposed alternatives are but indicators unique to country economies. In Peru, the balance of credit to the private sector represented 41.9 percent, down from 44.4 percent in 2022 (Central Reserve Bank of Peru, 2023). The size of the economy could be matter of exceptional concern to judge when credit is outgrowing the GDP. A credit-to-GDP gap —is often used as an early warning indicator for financial crises, with a widening gap suggesting potential instability. A credit-to-GDP gap data set aims at quantifying the notion of “excessive credit” in a simple way. It serves as an early warning indicator for potential banking crises or severe distress (Bank for International Settlement, undated).

The excess of credit to GDP from credit creating corporations can be assessed as a measure of the difference between the current ratio of credit-to-GDP and its historical trend, otherwise known as the credit to GDP gap. Corporate credit often dominates total credit in the economy. Some sectors benefit more than others. In Seychelles most from loans from the banking sector in 2017 were building & construction, tourism and private household (Central Bank of Seychelles, 2017). In Saudi Arabia utility sector and real estate activity takes more of corporate credits.

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2.1.3.2 Macro prudential Dimension: Current Accounts Deficits in EMDEs

Current account deficits give clear view of a dichotomy between a nation's merchandise exports and imports. In a broader view, current accounts deficits (CAD) present a coherent picture of transfer of financial wealth between residents and non-residents across borders. Where a country is in deficit the logical conclusion is that its residents transfer more wealth to nonresidents abroad due to payment for goods and services to the extent that residents' income paid to nonresidents is in surplus of the amount residents receive from rest of the world. Several African SSA economies report deficits on series periods prior to a temporary surplus. This is evident in oil exporting countries associating with OPEC⁵ (fig. 2.1.3.2 panel A). Latin America economies show long history of deficits (Panel B) almost equivalent to SSA economies⁶.

Extensive deficit indicates poor performance of the external sector, although the domestic economy has causal contribution to negative current accounts. A country running CAD implies that national saving (representing aggregate changes in tangible assets and changes in net financial assets) is lower than its investment ($I - S = CAD$). This could have dangerous consequences in the economy and the financial system to be specific. Devadas and

Loayaza (2018) indicate that CAD could have dual status- sustainable or unsustainable. It is argued that a current account deficit is sustainable when its underlying drivers support a smooth correction in the future. In a different view, Roubini and Wachtel (1999) argue that CAD is sustainable as long as no external sector crisis⁷ occurs. Conversely, it is unsustainable when it portrays symptoms of macroeconomic imbalances that would eventually trigger disruptive adjustments. Episode of unsustainability usually sets in when CAD appears to be large relative to GDP.

⁵ Cameroon is not a top member of OPEC, but it represents a dominant economy in Central African subregion. However, exclusion of Gabon and Equatorial Guinea is hinged on absence of reported data in WDI.

⁶ Panel C and D display current account deficits of big economies in SSA and transition Europe.

⁷ external sector crisis takes the form of exchange rate crisis or foreign debts crisis.

Figure 2.1.3.2: Current Account Deficits in Some Regions

Source: Author’s plot using data from WDI

There are outstanding literature pointing to the causal mechanisms leading to CAD eruption. Hervey and Merkel (2000) identify popular causal components using the U.S example. A hypothetical example highlights technological restructuring in a country. Foreign capital

inflow into an economy due to crisis in outflow economies explains CAD occurrence in the U.S. Magnitude of trade deficits are well known. However, sizeable and persistent current account imbalance could have consequences to the economy. This is not constrained to overall

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macroeconomic vulnerability alone rather destabilization of the financial system has been suspected and confirmed (Salvatore, 1998). This is especially when response to CAD through adjustment in credit growth and exchange rate precipitate domestic financial crisis (Shelburne, 2009). CAD has a feature capable of predicting systemic risks in the financial system. It could heighten to a peak that leaves the financial system vulnerable. The ultimate challenge is the fear of insolvency. A deficit economy and investors are concerned about an inability to repay accumulated foreign debts.

2.3 Empirical Reviews

Merrino, Lesame and Chondrogiannis (2024) examine how South Africa's credit market responses to macro prudential policy measures with the introduction of Basel III Accord in 2013 in South Africa. Specifically, the paper investigates whether financial stability objectives are achieved considering borrowers heterogeneity which could be at the expense of equitable credit allocation. The authors employ two-fold empirical strategy involving panel and time-series data between 2008 to 2013. Accordingly, the study reports that macro prudential policy has declined lending to households and majorly the poor households to the advantage of large business firms. Another finding also shows that bank regulatory framework under the Base III Accord triggers lenders' adverse selection by penalizing enterprises that are more creditworthy. Lastly, the study concludes that although Basel III has reduced reckless credit to consumers, it also has fault obvious in distributing finance in ways

that are not beneficial to long-run growth and financial stability.

Yadav et al. (2024) evaluate macro prudential policy efficacy in modulating housing sector bank credit as well as its impacts on banks assets quality in the Indian context. The paper employs bank-level quarterly data of 51 major banks for the period between Q1:2002 to Q3:2020. In addition, extends investigation to determine the impact of macro prudential policy actions across the different periods of the business and financial cycles, and by extension the monetary policy cycle. The result suggests that a tightening of macro prudential policy is effective in regulating bank credits flowing to the housing sector. The effect is statistically significant. For easing policy tightening, the coefficient was negative and statistically significant, revealing an increase in credit growth. Conversely, tightening showed stronger impact than easing. Focusing on response of macro prudential policy over business and financial cycles, policy measures are found to be more effective during high growth phase. But during different phases in the financial cycle, macro prudential policy on housing credit expansion fail to vary significantly. The study concludes that a tighter macro prudential policy in combination with a tighter monetary policy is helpful in curtailing housing sector non-performing assets.

Using industry-level data statistics in Peru, Madeira (2023) analyze causal impact of macro prudential policies on growth for 93 countries to overcome reverse-causality. Findings from the study indicate macro prudential tightening have inverse consequences on manufacturing

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growth, particularly in the long-run and for industries exhibiting high external finance dependence. The study concludes that negative impact of macro prudential tightening is stronger in periods of higher growth and for advanced countries. Škrinjarić (2024) introduce growth-at-risk (GaR) approach to measure macro prudential policy stance. The author conducts literature survey to examine theoretical papers. The paper observes that empirical research utilizes GaR to estimate the overall effects of MP on future economic growth. Turner (2018) presents macroeconomics of macro prudential policy. Using Bernanke-Blinder analytical model of closed economy the author asserts that analysis of macro prudential policy must take into consideration of market determined-interest rates. In the open economy it is the impact of capital flows. The author concludes that macro prudential policies sometimes respond to global macroeconomic variables beyond the reach of the local central bank. Cantú, Gambacorta and Shim (2020) focus on Asian-Pacific countries comprising (Australia, Indonesia, New Zealand, the Philippines and Thailand) to study effectiveness of macro prudential policies in the region. Using supervisory bank-level data, an empirical strategy involving meta-analysis finds that macro prudential policies adopted by countries in the region was impressive in cutting down on excess household credit growth. Guindos (2018) indicates that macro prudential policy is profoundly responsible for ensuring the stability of banking and overall financial system

across all individual financial institutions and over time.

Babihuga (2007) analyzes the relationship between macroeconomic and financial soundness indicators in a panel dataset of 96 countries covering 1998 to 2005. Generalized Method of Moment involving both differenced and system methods and also including the use of Two-stage-Least square are employed as econometric estimators. Findings indicate financial soundness indicators (FSI) strongly fluctuate with both the business cycle and the rate of inflation. The paper also finds evidence linking short term interest rates and real exchange rate as core determinants. In addition, the study concludes having observed heterogeneity in the relationship between macroeconomic factors and soundness of the financial system. These heterogeneities present in country and industry specific characteristics ranges from income levels, market concentration, financial depth to the quality of regulatory supervision. The study concludes that a negative correlation between business cycle and capital adequacy ratio varies across countries depending on their level of income and depth of the financial system.

3. Data and Econometric Specification

In our study design, this paper employs longitudinal paradigm design to deal with longitudinal data composition. It is fitting for a study involving cross section of subjects (Frees, 2003p.1-2). We adopt it as part of a broad range of study designs describing our empirical strategy. Under this scenario our choice is informed considering repeated collection of data on study variables at repeated interval

which is an indication that longitudinal process is established. Hofer and Sliwinski (2006) indicate that longitudinal data contain information necessary to directly address within-person change processes⁸. By so doing it carries greater wealth of information on study subjects, hence, its remarkable application. Consequently, we view such stance as a critical factor why, perhaps, it has been exploited in development of previous empirical papers in the course of advancing theory.

International Monetary Fund (IMF) Financial Access Survey (FAS) and World Development Indicators (WDI) available in World Bank databases are sources for data generation. On countries with missing data, the central bank publishes residual cross-country data. To be specific, African countries under monetary union whose data are completely unavailable in IMF are retrieved from West African Monetary Agency (WAMA), BEAC for CEMAC and BCEAO for WAMU.

Our sample countries are predominantly Emerging Markets and Developing Economies (EMDEs). We employ financial soundness indicator (FSI) variable computed by International Monetary Fund (IMF) on yearly frequency. The FSI is quantitatively reduced to minimum Core Equity Tier 1 (CET 1) ratio capital to risk-weighted assets. National bodies have autonomous capacity to set regulatory

minimum. CET 1 capital is the highest quality capital, and is sufficiently stable to absorb losses and ensure business continuity for the institution (UMOA, 2019).

Longitudinal and quantitative study designs direct and detect what econometric method is appropriate. Panel data features are in conformity with these paradigms. The issue on appropriate estimation method that is justifiable is based on literature. Baltagi (2008) provides persuasive reasons underscoring the application of panel data in econometric modelling. Therefore, data pooled from 102 LICs and MICs countries are estimated with panel data econometric technique. However, insufficient data availability in some countries (Sierra Leone, Azerbaijan, Afghanistan, Iran, Guinea, India, Saotome and Principi, Zimbabwe, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Benin, Angola, Chad, Equatorial Guinea, Guinea Bissau, Mauritania, Lao PDR and several others in the classification) compels our application of unbalanced panel data. This is not a strange practice in empirical investigations constrained by data vacuums.

A general form of panel data model adopted for analyzing policy conditions impacting banking system soundness is generally specified in equation (I):

$$FSI_{i,t} = f(\text{Creditboom}_{i,t}, \text{Current deficits}_{i,t}, \text{Nonperform}_{i,t}, \text{Bcycle}_{i,t}, \text{Interest}_{i,t}) \quad (I)$$

Where; FSI depicts financial soundness indicator, being measure to proxy banking system soundness. Creditboom Denotes credits boom, Current deficits implies current account deficits. Nonperform Depicts nonperforming

⁸ within-person change in our case represents periodic information variations within similar study variable. For instance, financial soundness indicator proxying banking system soundness changes within itself if it is considered as flow variable. Baltes and Nesselroade (1979) offer five rationales for adoption of longitudinal research to provide framework for developmental theory and aging.

loans; Bcycle means business cycle whereas Interest signifies interest rates. We substitute some variables in equation (I) using numeric representative indicators with the objective of narrowing systemic risk. This is expressed in equation (II):

$$CET1_{i,t} = f(\text{loan}_{GDP_{i,t}}, \text{Current deficits}_{i,t}, \text{Nonperform}_{i,t}, \text{Bcycle}_{i,t}, \text{Interest}_{i,t})$$

(II)

Where: $CET1_{i,t}$ represents common equity tier 1 estimated from risk-weighted assets (RWA). By substituting FSI for $CET1$, we recognize that common equity which is the ratio between hard core capital and risk-weighted assets is the ultimate indicator of bank resilience. Central banks have shown that Tier 1 capital⁹ is the highest-quality capital that is sufficiently stable for losses absorption and enable financial institutions to continue as a going concern (UMOA, 2023). Bcycle is not observed rather we extract it from a detrended gross domestic product using standard Hodrick-Prescott filter consistent with Harvey and Trimbur (2008). Inclusion of business cycle is informed by its capacity to proxy economic cycle as representative of economic volatility. Advantageously, it presents holistic view of rate of economic activity. Based on theoretical

insight in Phillips curve model, an economy's activity is gauged either by the unemployment rate or the output gap.¹⁰ We acknowledge that most debate on volatility is anchored on price inflation¹¹. In the present study economic volatility is proxied using output fluctuations computed as a percentage of potential GDP to derive output gap whose deviation from actual GDP constitute cyclical component. Our computation technique is a univariate non-structural approach consistent with Turkmen and Harun (2012). Loan-to-GDP denotes credit boom as instrument of procyclicality. Subscript i and t depict country and time factors respectively.

We estimate a dynamic panel data regression model incorporating country fixed effects using standard Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) developed by Arellano and Bond (1991) implemented in Akinci and Olmstead-Rumsey (2018). Instrumental Variable (IV) is a standard solution to endogeneity problem where an IV is strictly instrumental in the regression on the condition that it has no correlation with the unobserved error variable. This method under the framework of panel Generalized Method of Moment (GMM) which

⁹In financial institution capital classification from the Basel Accords there consists different streams of capital category. As widely adopted in existing literature and in the current analysis, tier 1 capital consists of permanent shareholders' equity and disclosed reserves. According to BIS (1988, 1996), tier 2 capital consists of undisclosed reserves, revaluation reserves general provisions and loan-loss reserves, hybrid debt-equity capital instruments, and subordinated long-term debt (over five years); Tier 3 capital consists of subordinated short-term debt (over two years)

¹⁰ defined as the deviation of the current level of output from its full employment or potential level. Phillips curve equation formulation shows that short-term movements in inflation is determined by output gap.

¹¹ quantity theory of money predicts that undesired growth in the stock of money will lead to higher inflation in the economy. This makes inflation a monetary phenomenon in the Monetarist insight (see for instance, Friedman (1957). National supervisory authorities calculate inflation based on consumer price index to track level overinflated prices of basked of goods in the economy. Also see for instance, Banco de Cabo Verde (2017) on macroeconomic and financial environment.

could either be differenced- GMM or system-GMM is suitable to eliminate endogeneity that influences efficiency of estimates whose hypothetical parameter sign may not be theoretically appealing. We jointly consider these two standard variants of GMM. The GMM model equation is expressed in the general form below:

$$C_{it} = \alpha C_{it-1} + \beta X_{it} + \omega_i + \varepsilon_{it}$$

(III)

Where the corresponding parameters are as already known. ω_i Depicts country-specific time-invariant factor in each cross-section of EMDEs. C_{it-1} Lagged dependent variable is an internal instrument. We expand equation (III) into a new equation replicating Babihuga (2007):

$$FSI_{it} = \alpha FSI_{it-1} + \beta_1 \text{Loan_gdp}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{Currentdeficit}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{Nonperform}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{Bcycle}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{Interest}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

(IV)

Equation (IV) is for panel data $i = 1, 102$ and $t = 2016, 2023$. Theoretical relationship between vector of explanatory variables and soundness requires taking optimal care in producing plausible economic interpretation. There is possible ambiguity and dilemma in providing theoretical economic linkage. Each parameter is prone to inherent theoretical case. However, a normative interpretation procedure suggests evaluating the parameters based on whether supervisory authorities had been keen on tightening or loosening macro prudential policy stance. Bebczuk et al (2011) provide robust safeguard in producing empirical interpretation of hypothetical economic signs of the correlation between instruments of macro

prudential policy and possible outcome variable. The authors relied on simple contemporaneous correlation. Positive values of model explanatory variables fairly indicate macro prudential tightening as regulatory proactive action to secure resilience of banking system, while negative values indicate an easing.

Furthermore, power of the model is complicated by integrating regulatory governance (an index constructed by the World Bank) as interaction term. Bolstering the health of the financial system is a continuous exercise. Gaganis et al. (2020) indicate that bank regulation interacting with governance holistically tackles bank excessive risk-taking. Mirzaei and Samet (2022) prove that effectiveness of macro prudential policy lies in its capacity to limit credit growth conditional on the quality of bank regulation and supervision. The authors interacted macro prudential policy with bank regulation. We follow similar procedure to re-specify a linear model. Therefore, the benchmark regression with interaction is:

$$FSI_{it} = \alpha FSI_{it-1} + \beta_1 \text{Loan_gdp}_{it} * \text{REGV} + \beta_2 \text{Currentdeficit}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{Nonperform}_{it} * \text{REGV} + \beta_4 \text{Bcycle}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{Interest}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

(V)

4. Discussion of Selected Results

We first discuss descriptive properties of banking soundness indicator. Table1A is a summary of standard descriptive statistics on transition economies to present regulatory compliance and comparison between risk-weighted assets (RWA) minimum capital requirement of 8% as a benchmark for countries in transition. We can clearly see the

level of compliance with capital requirement of 8% RWA in transition countries. The rate shows that capital sufficiency of their financial system is capable of containing adverse macro prudential conditions. For instance, Uzbekistan banking system has remained resilient. Central Bank of Uzbekistan (2023) highlighted that capital adequacy ratio was higher than the minimum requirements set by the Central Bank of Uzbekistan (CBU). Banks had sufficient capital for lending and absorbing potential losses. However, Azerbaijan 2% is linked to data inadequacy and does not fully represent the ideal minimum capital requirement prevailing in its financial system. Russian mean capital adequacy is only marginally above BCBS minimum with a mean of 9.29375% which grew to 13.07%. Nevertheless, Russian banking system is stable in terms of its banking system to capacity to collapse due to risky shocks.

Vietnam’s mean of 10.31% is also relatively sufficient. Estonia’s 26.9% is richly stable to respond to any risk irrespective of its magnitude. This might indicate the regulatory capacity of Estonia supervisors in enforcing compliance with international standard.

China as a giant economy modestly exceeded 8% in its 12.80875%. Its maximum of 14.7% is not exceptionally in excess of standard benchmark. In same class of economies in transition- Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Lithuania, Romania and Cambodia are within the range of 15 to 21% of mean regulatory minimum. Generally, economies in transition have robust financial system stability that survives key risk conditions. Smaller economies tend to be more stable in their capital provision. However, all the countries have financially stable banking sector that absorbs risks without compromising financial intermediation.

Table 1A: Descriptive statistics on Financial System Stability for Economies in Transition

Economies	Financial Stability Indicator			
	Mean	Std. Dev	Min.	Max.
Albania	15.41	6.299599	0	18.32
Armenia	16.02375	6.593501	0	20.32
Azerbaijan	2.41	6.81651	0	19.28
Belarus	16.095	6.607688	0	21.04
Bulgaria	18.89875	7.698121	0	22.74
Cambodia	19.17125	7.764694	0	22.66
China	12.80875	1.836452	10.5	14.7
Croatia	20.17625	8.3130650	0	25.58
Czech	14.69875	9.205896	0	22.11
Estonia	26.9	4.702279	21.2	34.5
Georgia	15.78625	6.636709	0	20.33
Hungary	16.19625	6.5685	0	19.59
Kazakhstan	19.54125	8.445343	0	26.96

Kyrgyzstan	21.4025	8.827609	0	28.16
Latvia	20.0425	8.391347	0	26.82
Lithuania	18.57875	7.829367	0	23.98
Roman	19.27875	8.012912	0	25.14
Russia	9.29375	5.744306	0	13.07
Slovenia	16.11	6.519211	0	19.15
Slovak	16.515	6.71277	0	19.81
Tajikistan	15.44125	9.784651	0	23.37
Uzbekistan	15.7925	6.89465	0	23.52
Viet Nam	10.31	4.192435	0	12.64
‡All economies	14.811	9.29979	-6.21	63.577

Note: Std Dev. denotes standard deviation; Max. Is maximum; Min. implies minimum

‡ All 102 economies classified as low or middle income countries

Table 1B: Descriptive statistics on Financial System Stability for Economies in Transition

Economies	Financial Stability Indicator				Obs.
	Mean	Std. Dev	Min.	Max.	
Angola	7.8875	11.00113	0	24.24	8
Benin	9.6875	6.011522	0	14.1	8
Botswana	16.84625	6.947538	0	21.86	8
Burkina Faso	9.6875	6.011522	0	14.1	8
Burundi	5.6875	10.53306	0	23.12	8
Cameroun	10.41625	4.746562	0	15.03	8
Cape Verde	16.0875	6.955047	0	22.2	8
Central Africa Republic	26.55125	5.516149	18.9	34.3	8
Chad	8.925	6.734822	-1.4	18.02	8
Comoros	14.525	12.28431	0	27.9	8
Congo, DR	8.23125	6.861227	0	14.34	8
Congo, Republic.	20.0225	8.784818	0	29.64	8
Cote d'Ivoire	9.6875	6.011522	0	14.1	8
Djibouti	12.92125	5.536452	0	17.07	8
Equatorial Guinea	9.82	16.48994	-6.21	31.79	8
Eswatini	19.8875	9.003408	0	31.58	8
Ethiopia	11.82	10.05706	10.05706	23.22	8
Gambia	27.77875	11.75407	0	37.49	8

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Ghana	16.53	7.015326	0	21.95	8
Guinea		12.2325	7.687239	0	18.47
8					
Guinea-Bissau		9.6875	6.011522	0	14.1
Kenya	16.495	6.011522	0	19.74	8
Lesotho		20.0675	2.655032	17.16	23.99
8					
Liberia		17.9825	12.28031	0	31.53
8					
Madagascar	10.985	4.574188	0	13.65	8
Malawi		17.87875	7.416835	0	22.43
8					
Mali		9.6875	6.011522	0	14.1
Mauritania	0	0	0	0	8
Mauritius	17.10625	6.962655	0	20.67	8
Mozambique	20.24	10.28136	0	28.78	8
Namibia	13.28625	5.670838	0	16.97	8
Niger		9.6875	6.011522	0	14.1
8					
Nigeria		12.3	5.197945	0	15.21
8					
Rwanda	21.0625	1.389694	20	23.8	8
Sao Tome and Principe*	0	0	0	0	8
Senegal		9.6875	6.011522	0	14.1
8					
Seychelles	16.25875	10.42071	0	26.61	8
Sierra Leone*	0	0	0	0	8
South Africa	12.445	7.709981	0	18.11	8
South Sudan*	0	0	0	0	8
Sudan*	0	0	0	0	8
Tanzania	19.05	1.13641	17.9	20.9	8
Togo		9.6875	6.011522	0	14.1
8					
Uganda		19.13625	7.824489	0	23.67
8					
Zambia		20.5525	8.58259	0	26.48
8					
Zimbabwe	25.4825	15.98935	0	37.51	8
‡All economies	14.811	9.29979	-6.21	63.577	8

In the table 1B computation of FSI for SSA countries some of the national jurisdictions maintained FSI above regulatory minimum of 8%. Deviation of the mean from 8% especially when it is below BCBS 8% minimum may not

necessarily imply supervisory weakness at the micro prudential level but data gap has been a fundamental issue in certain countries. The mean of Angola minimum capital is 7.8875% with a maximum of 24.24%. While BCBS

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requires that all national jurisdictions peg their minimum capital capable of absorbing shocks of any amplitude is seen to be relatively weak as it is below average. The exceptionally large maximum underscores that fact that Angola banking system is safe and sound for confidence. Benin marginally exceeded regulatory minimum given a mean of 9.6875% and excessive maximum of 14.1%. Botswana exceptionally exceeded the minimum given a mean of 16.84625% which indicates capital sophistication. Burundi's 5.6875% is below 8% requirement. A normative view based on available data is that Burundi financial system is not capitally sophisticated as required according to the terms of conventionally fixed minimum requirement.

Gambia is a small country but has outperformed expectation recording 27.778% and as high as 37.49% which sufficiently insulates its financial system from shocks from the three shock areas which the entire financial system is vulnerable to. Nigeria has a mean of 12.3% with a peak of 15.21% as a big economy marking approximately 4.3% in excess. The financial system is relatively secure based on BCBS capital requirement of 8%. South Africa has a mean of 12.445% to show that its banking system is stable to overcome potential shocks. Generally, the means of smaller economies tend to be significantly higher than the larger economies. Thus, sample African countries show sign of robust capital capacity. Chad and Democratic Republic of Congo individually record CAR of 8.925% and 8.231% in the threshold of BCBS 8%. This is a strong indication that the means are prone to sudden

drop risking their financial systems. Furthermore, Zambia central latest 2024 stress test report shows that it banking sector remains adequately capitalized (Bank of Zambia, 2024). The mean of CAR of 20.5525% for Zambia supports BoZ stress test report. A review from a major economy like Nigeria oversight of the five (5) Domestic Systemically Important Banks (D-SIBs) reveals that all the D-SIBs complied with the minimum capital adequacy and liquidity ratio requirements of 15% and 30% respectively (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2021).

4.1 Baseline Regression Results Discussion

In the baseline scenario, we have combined in line with regression equations (I) and (II) several macro prudential conditions that potentially molest the soundness of the banking system in a 102 sample EMDEs with known income size. Ordinary Least Square model, Difference Generalized Method of Moments (D-GMM), Within-Group estimator, System Generalized Method of Moments (SYS-GMM) and Two-stage Least Square (TSLS) have been combined to obtain superior estimation in view of comparison and complementary purposes. The last two identification strategies are scarcely implemented because both estimators are cumbersome. Superiority of estimate in this regard covers consistence, efficiency; accounting for individual heterogeneity, higher precisions and instrument validity vital in solving problem of endogeneity in regressors auto correlating with disturbance term. The multiple method combination especially with the inclusion of system-GMM is methodologically important in estimating

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dynamic panel data. In particular, Arellano and Bover (1995); Blundell and Bond (1998); Blundell, Bond and Windmeijer (2001); Blundell and Bond (1995) have had deep influence in econometric of estimation using system GMM to improve the performance and

properties of standard first-differenced GMM. All the variables represent various categories of macro and micro prudential indicators depicting capital adequacy and capital quality, balance of payments, GDP-to-credit, and assets quality.

Table 2: Comparative Baseline Scenario on Banking System Soundness Regression

Dependent Variable: FSI	OLS TSL	Within Group	Difference-GMM	SYS-GMM
FSI (-1)	(0.775738)*** (1.471199)	(0.588475)***	(2.210406)*	(1.471199)
Current Deficit (log)	[0.0000] [0.4162]	[0.0000]	[0.0659]	[0.5269]
Business cycle (log)	(0.058248) (-1.483187)	(0.113657)	(-3.962075)	(-1.483187)
Interest Rate	[0.5409] [0.8929]	[0.8511]	[0.1541]	[0.8717]
Credit boom	(0.130336)*** (1.37E-10)	(-0.355046)	(0.330336)	(1.37E-10)
Nonperforming loan	[0.0005] [0.9810] (-0.070602)* (-1.005207)	[0.2524]	[0.5780]	[0.9731]
	[0.0590] [0.2656] (5.17E-11) (4.59E-10)	[0.0088]	[0.0456]	[0.3033]
	[0.1414] [0.6379] (0.184732)*** (1.347951)	[0.1527]	[0.9037]	[0.7442]
	[0.0005] [0.5746]	[0.0133]	[0.8862]	[0.5914]
Prob(F-statistic)		0.0000		DW 1.28297
Adj-R ²	0.544251	0.558778		0.626333
J-statistic			6.050902	
Prob(J-statistic)			0.417512	
Observation/unbalanced	832 263	832		263

() represents slope coefficient, * significant at 10%, ** significant at 5%, *significant at 1%, [] denotes p-value**

Beginning with lagged dependent variable all models confirm persistence of financial stability indicator which validates existence and importance of history. The lag is significant at 1%, 5% and 10% levels. Accordingly, it is argued that capital adequacy ratios are lagged indicators of banking problems and by the moment capital adequacy ratios show a decline, financial institutions generally have already been experiencing serious problems (Hilbers et al. 2000). As the coefficient of lagged dependent variable of 2.210406% computed with D-GMM which is greater than 0.588475% in within group estimator it is logical to conclude that D-GMM display greater estimation power. The high positive and high statistical significance of lagged dependent variable across all models is a confirmation of models' dynamic quality. This conforms to the conclusion found in Kjosevski and Petkovski (2017). Similarly, system-GMM and two stage least square produced identical estimates. However, given high J-statistics of 0.417512 the model is over identified proving its analytical plausibility and efficiency. As evident in Nookhwun (2017) introducing lagged dependent variable provide platform to account for potential endogeneity in MPI. Thus, the lag dependent variable is a strong instrument. Note that the coefficient of the persistent parameter also warrants the use of D-GMM as a robust estimator. The one-period lag financial stability indicator is confirmed to be a robust internal instrumental variable based on D-GMM. In the D-GMM column, current account deficit,

interest rate and credit boom are negative. Nonperforming loans and business cycle are positive. Current account deficit (CAD) in the BOP has adverse consequences on the resilience of banking sector. Because hypothesis at 10% shows insignificance, it might indicate that current account deficit is yet to arrive to the point of excessive degree in predicting fragility. Sources of this characteristic have long emerged but divided into temporary and structural factors underlining a country's current account position (Calderón, Chong, & Loayza, 1999; Augusto, 2002). CAD must change to both external and internal conditions of foreign trading partner and its home macroeconomic dynamics. An impressive number of theoretical literature and empirics show that CAD is not peculiar to poor economies. For instance, Anoruo and Ramchander (1998) to five developing Southeast Asian economies— India, Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia and the Philippines acknowledges similar condition. Blanchard (2007) in rich countries— Spain and Portugal are known instances. Osakwe and Verick (2007) for Sub-Saharan Africa. Shelburne (2008) for Greece, Spain and Portugal. Freund and Warnock (2007); Chen (2011) for G-7 countries and OECD. Salvatore (1998) in emerging markets. Coughlin, Pakko and Poole (2006); Engel and Rogers (2006) for the US. Price inflation of foreign goods entry into LICs and MICs within countries in same category caused by trade is a potential source of the information embedded in current result.

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Unprecedented trade deficits breed challenge in current account that could account for financial system fragility especially as banks lend almost irredeemable debts either in foreign currency or domestic currency. Minsky (1978) financial instability hypothesis (FSH) which could be the backbone of current account deficit interpretations seems to suggest that debt explained in FSH constituting instability element could be traced to massive external trade deficits in current accounts.

Credit boom has negative repercussion on stability. It could be that the gap between its long-term trend and actual ratio is expanding in such magnitude that crisis can be envisaged. Borio and Lowe (2005, 2007) show that the gap is a useful symbol of early warning. Our result supports this notably held view that credit boom gap is an early warning indicator (EWI) to indicate financial vulnerabilities. Thus, aggressive credit expansion not minding size of national outputs renders financial firms vulnerable. Interest rate is positive and significant at 10%. The coefficients conflicts with negative a priori expectation. The result indicates these variables are not capable of disrupting and dislocating financial intermediation by throwing banking system stability into devastation. The significance of interest rate which though failed to deteriorate capital quality of the banking system shows that either its rate has not increased to the level it becomes risky to credits. It could also be that defaults have not been widely recorded to the extent that systemic risk is imminent.

Nonperforming loans (NPLs) has a coefficient of 0.092068 suggesting positive consequence

on financial system stability. This is clearly an anomaly. NPLs of any magnitude deteriorates balance sheets. Occasional managerial offences of ever greening conceals the true information about failing credits quality of some banks due to management deliberate misclassification. It might probably imply stringent supervision. Going by its significance at 5% this finding is in conformity with Aulia et al. (2023) findings that NPLs in Indonesia exerts significant influence on conventional commercial bank stability. In addition, given its positive coefficient, NPLs estimate could suggest that aggregate nonperforming loans in the sample countries are quite minimal to harm financial stability which is the case in Oman financial system and Cambodia (Central Bank of Oman, 2024; National Bank of Cambodia, 2024). It could be loosely interpreted that positive NPLs as reported in Kazakhstan economy could be a reflection of the view that quality of loans is improving across all business entities (National Bank of Kazakhstan, 2023).

However, a note of caution is that the positive coefficient which normatively indicates that NPL improves stability defies theoretical logic. It possesses latent capacity to deteriorate a banking system with healthy level of capitalization and resilience equipped to absorb shock losses. It is quite the opposite in Central African Republic whose assets quality depreciated to 16.2% NPLs ratio (International Monetary Fund, 2024). Probably, NPLs result could imply that the banking system of countries in MICs and LICs are still positioned

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to withstand shocks of any magnitude¹². Buoyant regulatory and supervisory management is likely responsible for the lack of negative implication of deteriorating loans on FSI. It is also curious to guess that bad loans may not have escalated to the level it is technically risky enough to trigger deterioration of banking system soundness. This conflicts with inverse association in previous studies Ozili (2019). Nevertheless, severely impaired loans remain a risky asset factor to system soundness.

¹² central bank of nations reason in this line. For instance, Omani central bank shows that NPL in the financial system remained low where solvency is not compromised.

Table 3: Regression with Regulatory Governance Interaction

Dependent Variable: FSI	OLS GMM	Within Group TSLS	Difference-GMM	SYS-
FSI (-1)	(0.807448)***	(0.513553)**	(0.551544)	(2.088891)
Current account Deficit (log)	(2.088891)	(0.142038)	(-1.422160)*	(1.50E-09)
Business cycle (log)	(-0.042557)	(-0.316629)	(0.159859)	(2.55E-16)
Interest Rate	(0.082173)**	(-0.153700)**	(-0.642230)	(-0.257052)
Credit boom*reg	(-0.055153)	(3.31E-10)	(2.40E-10)	(-1.87E-10)
Nonperforming loan* reg	(-8.61E-11)*	(-0.665797)***	(-1.329267)**	(1.752300)
	(-0.195780)***			
	(1.752300)			
Prob(F-statistic)		0.000000		DW 2.270419
Adj-R ²	0.489522	0.519452		
J-statistic			18.51767	
Prob(J-statistic)			0.01756	

() represents slope coefficient * significant at 10%, ** significant at 5%, *significant at 1%**

An econometric interaction as can be seen in table 3 between certain macro prudential policy metrics with governance indicator in equation (V) to measure influence of robust monitoring and supervision¹³ yields impressive findings. The table 3 presents modest modification in prior estimation. In broader view, the result represents an estimated parsimonious model,

with financial stability indicator in previous year as a function of macroeconomic variables including business cycle, nonperforming loans, current account deficits, interest rate and credit boom. Regulatory governance interaction changed the dynamics of the initial findings. The first result worthy of note is that internal instrumental variable on difference-GMM regression is invalid for the whole sample. The J-statistics probability rejects the null to validate moment condition over identification

¹³ Notice that business cycle, current accounts deficits have no interaction with regulatory governance. This is because regulatory governance is designed to predominantly manage financial system and institutions in it.

but its persistent parameter is insignificant. However, the inconsistency in D-GMM supports the suspicion and conviction that within-Group estimator given F-statistic of 0.00000 which is unrejected at 1% level is a valid estimator. Within group estimator accounts for time invariant heterogeneity on cross sections. Evidently, a marginal variation in current account deficits indicates positive implication in quality of financial system soundness by approximately insignificant amount of 0.142038%. The finding defies a priori expectation. It could be that powerful manufacturing economies of China and others reported significant surpluses in their current accounts. Peoples Republic of China has high share of global trade. Perhaps if China is deleted from the model current account deficits could prove that it has deteriorating properties risking financial system stability.

Business cycle produced similar negative evidence but it is also insignificant given a coefficient of -0.316629%. Adverse cyclical climate in the economic system heading in the path of underproduction could inject harmful features against banking system soundness. Loans repayment partially depends on borrower capacity to draw resources from value of national outputs. But where the economy is stagnating nonperforming loans grow. This might implicitly explain the negative result on nonperforming loans as it appears regulatory governance effort is undermined by economic fragility. Studies have shown that banking stability and macro economy are closely linked. Our result is corroborating this. In addition, this empirical and theoretical evidence comply

with Kaufman (2001) insights that banking system crisis is influenced by downturn in the economy, hence, outstandingly validating a strong link of both concepts. The author also asserted that instability in banking and financial market is associated with macro instability. Finding on business cycle is consistent with the conclusions of Jónsson, Sigurðsson and Kristjánisdóttir (2024) that business cycle is disruptive to financial stability but through implementation of governmental financial and monetary policy regimes. The result suggests that economic cyclicalities are harmful to financial stability of the banking sector when regulatory governance interacts with credit boom and nonperforming loans. The evidence is insignificant across all probability statistics. However, it has crucial bearing on judging capital adequacy robustness in the banking system of sample countries. As business cyclicalities persist in trajectory of fluctuations financial stability further deteriorates dragging financial intermediation into systemic risk vulnerability. As consistent with Abildgren (2012), persistent decline in real GDP characterizes financial crisis of which economic recovery after a banking crisis tend to be slower than normal in Danish post-Second World War economic history.

Credit boom shows that adjustment using regulatory pressure neither adversely affected private sector credit growth level nor did it end up causing deteriorating implications on banking system soundness. For instance, under condition of robust regulatory governance to manage credit expansion vis-à-vis the size of the economy, the dynamic effect is positive but

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weakly significant at 10% level. In reality credit boom has limited information to this effect. Meanwhile regulatory governance via the control of credit expansion is ideal for protecting banking system soundness. This is theoretically valid with respect to positive known outcome. Regulatory governance clearly mitigates extreme credit booms, thus, helping financial system by-pass potential risks that damage soundness. This beneficial consequence is documented in Guérineau and Léon (2019) for low income and advanced economies. An outstanding regulatory consequence is that it directly improves credit portfolio quality which is consistent with findings documented in Guérineau and Léon (2016) confirming that credit information sharing system reduces financial fragility. This is akin to regulatory governance which is keenly interested on credit information. Therefore, our finding holds even in MICs and LICs.

Interacting interest rate with regulatory governance has a negative coefficient of -0.15370 (15.37%) at 1%, 5% and 10% indicating a substantial decline in the financial soundness of bank sector in MICs and LICs. One explanation offered to gain insight into this could be that interest rate grew higher than necessary to the extent that it becomes a risk factor. Rapid expansion in credit relative to the size of the economy when interest rates decline to low levels could become harmful leading to a jump in non-performing loan ratio that worsened in bad times. Asymmetric theoretical view could explain the negative coefficient of interest rate in a market with less transparency. Higher rate in some economies motivates

adverse selection in bank credit portfolio construction and rebalancing. Bank loans contract covers both interest rate and collateral which are paramount in credit analysis in a market with asymmetric information. Higher interest rate presents opportunity for exploitative tendencies which is a core message of asymmetric information (Akerlof, 1970). There is higher probability that loans will go bad when shocks to cost of credits makes bank loans exorbitant. If this is the reality, higher interest rate induced adverse selection renders fragile banking system soundness.

Nonperforming loans interacted with regulatory governance has inverse relationship that complies with Sotiropoulou, Giakoumatos and Petropoulos (2019) negative findings. It underscores the fact that NPLs ratio having a coefficient of -0.520962 (52.09%) is a strong micro-prudential risk factor made evident when regulatory governance interacts with credit boom and NPL variables. The current result appears to be theoretically strange as it defies a priori expectation. This is because regulatory governance is designed to put financial fragility under check by keeping NPLs low. Where monetary policy rate gets hiked it weakens debt servicing ability of households and businesses, thus, making negative NPLs a possibility that adversely damages banking system soundness. Liberia is one of the countries with large NPLs of 17.2% in 2019 and 21.2% in 2020 (Central Bank of Liberia, 2020). However, regulatory governance reduces NPLs ratio and could be a likely reason why in our sample economies the banking system have very low NPLs and far below prudential

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thresholds (Bank of Jamaica, 2023). In several banking systems NPLs is a strong hindrance to robust banking regulatory capital. Especially in some LICs and arguably in some MICs, the regulatory system could be somewhat fragile. This could be the reason behind negative NPLs ratio against soundness. Thus, where regulatory governance fails to strictly manage NPLs, it turns out that NPL ratio fuels banking system fragility making it highly undesirable for any economy.

5. Final Concluding Remarks

Macro prudential policy tools operate on mitigating systemic risks in order to protect the real economy from financial system-based risks. What is modestly known is that sources of systemic risks partly erupt from faulty operational mechanisms in financial corporations and partly from the macroeconomic dynamics- domestic and foreign. Critical measures of macro prudential policy sheds lights on its empirical effectiveness in managing and averting banking system fragility. Low and Middle Income economies are embracing active use of macro prudential interventions which practically dependent on a country's level of financial development embedded in regulatory responsibilities of each jurisdiction. However, each measure provides differing information about its crucial effects on financial soundness of banking system in 102 countries. Credit boom carries adverse repercussion that undermines financial stability with capacity to drive systemic destabilization in bank dominated financial system. The likely deep mismatch between nominal credits growth and GDP could have

been inferentially unsustainable in some sample countries' economy. Nonperforming loan is a direct opposite especially with improvement in certain jurisdiction, yet it has capacity to impair banking soundness if negligently left unchecked. Current account deficit in the balance of payments has adverse consequences on the resilience of banking sector. Evidently, certain macro-financial elements complicate functional integrity of any banking system.

An integral aspect is the joint influence of robust regulatory governance implementation and compliance vis-à-vis interaction with forces of macro prudential policy. On this account, credits boom responds positively to robust governance making regulatory supervision and monitoring a necessity for upholding banking system soundness. It further shows proven effectiveness in managing latent capacity of current account deficits in damaging soundness of banks in LICs and MICs. However, it failed as regards to the management of nonperforming loans in minimizing it risks while stabilizing banks prone to crisis from default risks. Regulatory governance has no capacity in dealing with business cycle nor capable of preventing it from ruining financial stability of countries in developing and emerging markets. This tend to prove that cyclicity appeared to be beyond the managerial scope of central bank monetary policy. In other words, business cycle is an adverse macroeconomic factor which yet, calls macro prudential authorities to act in a countercyclical way. Thus, further literature is needed to understand how policy tool like

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countercyclical capital buffers reverse the vulnerability for sustained liquidity supply of

the banking sector.

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